

Case Study Protocol.

This case study protocol has been conducted following Yin (2003), Brereton et al. (2008) and Pucihar et al. (2015) reporting items when applicable to a qualitative research project at hand. Best practices of the PRISMA-P reporting of systematic reviews have also been applied (e.g. Shamseer et al., 2008), where applicable. The document contains information and instructions for carrying out and reporting a dissertation project called Healthcare musicians 2016–2022, and especially the information on synthesizing individual case studies as a multiple case study. Protocol includes research methods and steps and serves as such a handbook, or a meta plan (Lehtinen-Schnabel, 2019), for conducting a non-medical, qualitative multiple case study within the project that was conducted in healthcare environments.

This protocol has been created subsequently after the data generation* for the following reasons:

1. To analyse and synthesize systematically the multiple case study at hand.
2. To bridge knowledge in-between practitioner level and organizational level.
3. To facilitate future research projects and analyze data with multiple sources of evidence, as well as knowledge produced within social networks.
4. To synthesize knowledge in-between micro, meso and macro levels, as well as create better understanding and articulation in-between practitioner, organizational, as well as policy/systematic levels within the topic.
5. To create systematic knowledge in the fields of arts and health, healthcare musicians' work, as well as expanding and hybrid professionalism in music education.

*In-between years 2016–2020 the research plan of the project was followed and served as a systematic presentation of the study

	Section 1: Administrative information
1.1 Identification	Case Study Protocol: Healthcare Musicians 2016–2022. The (Un)Settled Space of Healthcare Musicians: Developing Hybrid Professionalism in and through Music in the Finnish Healthcare System.
1.2 Update	The protocol was created on 4 th of January, 2021 (first draft on 1 st of August, 2020). For this version contact the author. The protocol information was modified on January 2 nd , 2022 as follows: 1.1 Identification : The title was revised. 2.4 Purpose and research question(s): The grounding research question wording was subtly revised.
	Registration
1.3 Registration and public protocol documents	No registration. Classification of this document is public, and it is published in Zenodo repository: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6325201 Public protocol documents include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A non-medical systematic review protocol https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3589993 • Data Management Plan DMP Tuuli https://taru12koivisto.wixsite.com/researcher/doctoral • Privacy Statement (GDPR Compliant Document) https://taru12koivisto.wixsite.com/researcher/doctoral • Interview data of the studies and data generation information / Finnish Social Science Data Archive (distributor) http://urn.fi/urn:nbn:fi:fsd:T-FSD3589

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1.4 Contact information	Corresponding author: Taru-Anneli Koivisto, taru.koivisto@uniarts.fi Author Affiliations: The Center for Educational Research and Academic Development in the Arts (CERADA), MuTri Doctoral School at the Sibelius Academy of the University of the Arts Helsinki, ArtsEqual Research Consortium
	Support
1.5 Sources	This multiple case study research was undertaken as part of the Arts as Public Service: Strategic Steps towards Equality (ArtsEqual) Research Initiative supported by the Academy of Finland’s Strategic Research Council (grant no. 293199). The ethical statement for the study, which is a sub-study of a doctoral dissertation of the author, was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of the Arts Helsinki (Feb 15, 2018). The research permit was granted by the HUS Helsinki and Uusimaa Hospital District, Children and Adolescents (June 18, 2018) and City of Espoo, Department of Social and Health Services (Apr 24, 2018).
1.6 Sponsor	The Mutri Doctoral School of Sibelius Academy and CERADA, University of the Arts Helsinki, are funding this multiple case study. Financial support has been provided by the Paulo Foundation, Signe and Ane Gyllenbergs Foundation, Zonta International District 20, the Alfred Kordelin Foundation, and Oskar Öflunds Stiftelse sr.
1.7 Role of sponsor and/or funder	The author has conducted the design of the protocol, analysis plan, the data generation, and analysis. The funders have had no input on the interpretation or publication of the study results.
	Section 2: Introduction
2.1 Background	Despite the new kinds of professional views and spaces that musicians and music educators are encountering in healthcare settings, the research literature concerning their professionalism and the aims and goals of their practices in special healthcare services require more examination and conceptualization. Professional views (beyond therapeutic goals) have remained scarcely researched, and music practices in hospital wards are mainly non-systematic. Increasing opportunities in novel sectors of society are also setting new goals for the research and education of music practitioners. This stems the global transformation of professional work in education, arts and health settings, and arts, as well.
2.2 Theoretical and conceptual framework	Considering national and international research, it is becoming increasingly clear that the so-called traditional art and art education fields are facing great turbulence (see Westerlund & Gaunt, 2021), and conventional premises of the field are lacking in the kind of philosophical and theoretical rigor required to approach the kind of “new professionalisms” as defined by Cribb & Gewirtz (2015). To explore music and music education as a basic cultural need and right, the research design involves social models of health (Wilkinson & Marmot, 2003; Belfiore & Bennett, 2007) that encourage us to take a step beyond so-called biomedical models of health (e.g., Ruud, 2013; Stige & Ansdell, 2015). The concept of hybrid professionalism (Gielen, 2009, see Lehtikainen, Pässilä & Owens, 2021) is used to build a solid basis for a reflexive (Alvesson & Sköldberg, 2017) methodological approach and hybrid identities in arts and health professions.

<p>2.3 Previous research on the topic</p>	<p>Previous research on music professionalism is covered through a qualitative systematic research (Koivisto & Tähti, 2021). Earlier research, as well as emerging conceptual and theoretical reviews are taken under each single case. Based on the literature, the professional frame explored within this research project includes following elements: describing healthcare musicians’ musical skills, competences, and relevant practitioner knowledge in healthcare settings; conceptualizing music practices and professional spaces; and exploring the professional identities of healthcare musicians.</p>						
<p>2.4 Purpose and research question(s)</p>	<p>The purpose of this qualitatively organized multiple case study is to discuss the work and professional space of healthcare musicians in the Finnish healthcare system, particularly in hospitals. To fulfil the purpose of the research, the established objectives are: 1) to explore the professional music making practices and activities healthcare musicians implement in the somatic hospital wards; 2) to map the interprofessional possibilities and challenges within the hospital organisations; and 3) to facilitate the arts and health policies, stakeholder collaboration and education in and in-between the arts organisations and the healthcare system.</p> <p>The grounding research question covering the multiple case study is: How does healthcare musicians’ work inform a new understanding of the practice and theory of music professionalism in a changing society?</p> <p>Following research questions will be asked in each sub-studies: Systematic review: 1) What kind of professional practices and professional space are represented in the reviewed literature concerning healthcare musicians’ work in somatic hospital wards? 2) According to the reviewed literature, in what ways can the work and professional space of healthcare musicians be conceptualized? Case 1) What kind of musicking as a professional practice emerges when music practitioners work in neonatal intensive care units? What kinds of metaphorical thinking and reflections are constructed through musicking situations, and how could these support music practitioners’ professional work in neonatal intensive care units? Case 2) How is the nature of the work in eldercare hospital wards reflected by the efforts of healthcare musicians? How may the understanding of these music professionals’ work contribute to the development of expanding professionalism in music and higher music education? Case 3) How do healthcare musicians support the patients, their families and healthcare personnel through professional music practices within end-of-life contexts? What kind of emotional work do healthcare musicians engage within end-of-life contexts in hospital wards?</p>						
<p>Section 3: Case study design</p>							
<p>3.1 Research approach</p>	<p>The research approach of the multiple case study is presented in the Figure 1 (see Diehl, Kuettner & Schubert, 2013; Pucihar, 2015; Stake, 1995; Yin, 2003). To meet project objectives phases of research are: 1) Planning, defining and designing the research; 2) Data generation; 3) Analysis, case presentations and publications; 4) Cross-case analysis / synthesizing kappa.</p> <p>Figure 1. Research approach.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="411 1870 1396 1975" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <tr> <td colspan="3" style="text-align: center;">Multiple case study</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">1. Define and design</td> <td style="text-align: center;">2. Prepare and collect</td> <td style="text-align: center;">3. Analyze and conduct</td> </tr> </table>	Multiple case study			1. Define and design	2. Prepare and collect	3. Analyze and conduct
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	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="411 217 683 600"> Review literature Develop theory Select cases Design data generation Implement pilot study </td> <td data-bbox="691 217 1066 600"> Conduct empirical research Hospital 1 (Eldercare hospital) Hospital 2 (Children’s hospital) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews • Participant observations • Professional narratives • Complementing interviews </td> <td data-bbox="1074 217 1388 600"> Write and publish individual case reports Case 1 Case 2 Case 3 </td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3" data-bbox="411 611 1388 645" style="text-align: center;">4. Analyze and synthesize</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3" data-bbox="411 656 1388 846" style="text-align: center;"> Draw cross-case conclusions Modify theory Develop policy implications Write cross-case report / synthesizing kappa </td> </tr> </table>	Review literature Develop theory Select cases Design data generation Implement pilot study	Conduct empirical research Hospital 1 (Eldercare hospital) Hospital 2 (Children’s hospital) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews • Participant observations • Professional narratives • Complementing interviews 	Write and publish individual case reports Case 1 Case 2 Case 3	4. Analyze and synthesize			Draw cross-case conclusions Modify theory Develop policy implications Write cross-case report / synthesizing kappa		
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<p>3.2 Types of cases</p>	<p>In this research project multiple case study approach is both, a methodology and a research strategy (Yin, 1994). By employing a holistic multiple-case design, the single studies may adopt an instrumental or intrinsic (e.g., in-depth or descriptive) nature. Rather than seeking direct replication, the cases represent the diversified working contexts of healthcare musicians, forming a basis for a stronger theoretical representation. As such, the analytical benefits, and possibilities to strengthen the findings by choosing more than one case are substantial (see Yin, 2003, 96). The research questions, guiding the research process as a whole, created a need for a highly reflexive research approach (Alvesson & Sköldbberg, 2017), where generic sampling for cases, or obtaining rigorous methodology is not realistic, or even relevant. Instead, to prove a common structure and consistency (see Brereton et al., 2008), crafting and shaping instruments and protocols was selected as a strategic tool.</p>									
<p>3.3 Selection criteria / eligibility</p>	<p>The study started in 2016–2017 by identifying the key healthcare musicians and hospitals contexts.</p> <p><i>Contexts.</i> The eligibility criteria for the participating hospitals were: 1) hospitals or hospital wards with necessary resources and will to collaborate with an external researcher; 2) hospitals that already had collaborated with healthcare musicians (i.e., the work was not conducted solely within a project or was not temporary in nature); 3) the music work took place in somatic hospital wards on a weekly basis; 4) the study could take place in-between 2018–2019, and 5) the research permit processes before the field work were likely to be conducted within the scope of one year.</p> <p><i>Participants.</i> Eligibility criteria for participating healthcare musicians, selected by using purposeful sampling strategy (Creswell, 2013), were: 1) a professional degree in music or music-related areas; 2) several years of experience in practicing music in healthcare and/or care settings; and 3) working experience in the somatic children wards, eldercare hospital wards, and/or hospice and palliative care. To develop the field and create a more rigid research framework, voluntary work was excluded from the study, as well as community musicians with no inservice training into health settings.</p>									

	<p>The individual case studies were identified as emerging from the empirical data. A key strategy was also simply to conduct cases in the environments where gatekeeping practices of the hospitals and healthcare personnel enabled the researcher to conduct a qualitative, non-medical research in the first place.</p> <p>After conducting the empirical part in two hospital contexts, a children’s hospital and an eldercare hospital, some complementing interviews took place, mainly through snowball sampling. The participants of the complementing interviews were selected based on the overarching research question, through exploring the possibilities of their expertise in enlightening the research topic.</p> <p><i>Study designs:</i> It was important to separate music therapy practice from the healthcare musicians’ work, since this agency often overlaps in the healthcare, and is often difficult for medical doctors, nurses and administration to separate and acknowledge. Also solely performing as a musician was excluded from the study designs, and music medicine (such as listening to recorded music in hospitals; music without participatory interaction as such being a factor and effect).</p> <p><i>Interventions:</i> Of interest were interventions in the frame of community music, care music, health musicking, music education, and musicianship. Out of the scope of the research are music for self-care, music in non-professional (voluntary) use, music medicine, music therapy, and trans-professional learning in medicine through music.</p> <p><i>Outcomes:</i> Outcomes will be analyzed and reported through reflexive methodology, and coded and synthesized through thematic analysis.</p>
	Section 4: Multiple case studies
4.1 Data generation methods	Data generation which does not separate a phenomenon from its contexts has many variables, which may have an impact to the analysis and outcomes of the study. The empirical part of the research project included interviews and participant observations of healthcare musicians, healthcare personnel, patients, and families in the hospital wards. Healthcare musicians wrote also professional narratives. Other materials, such as leaflets and other information brochures, produced by healthcare musicians and personnel, were collected, as well. The data is complemented with interviews such as administrative personnel in two collaborating organisations (healthcare clowns’ association and a symphony orchestra), a music therapist, and a community musician.
4.2 Data generation and storage	Interview and observation guidelines, as well as other background information on data generation is publicly stored in the Finnish Social Science Data Archive.
4.4 Methodological and ethical considerations	The research will have many possibilities and challenges in research methodology, as well as in ethics, ranging from individual “virtue ethics” to procedural ethics. To ensure ethically and methodologically high-level research, transparency and trustfulness in reporting is important, following ethical procedures such as RCR guidelines of the Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity (TENK, 2012), the ethical guidelines of the University of the Arts Helsinki (UNIARTS, 2015), and the code of ethics of the European Commission in research (EC, 2013). The anonymity and rights of the participants is important to protect, as well as treat them respectfully throughout the process.

4.5 Case study reports and cross-case analysis	All the cases will be published as individual research articles in international scholarly journals. After publishing, the cross-case analysis begins by utilizing case report form for individual cases (see Appendix 1: Case report instructions for a single case). After analyzing the findings from a conceptual and theoretical viewpoint, the synthesis of the cases will be produced by: 1) Analyzing (reflexively) variables in the context of the case; 2) generalizing beyond the single case; 3) working the analysis from ground up; and 4) examining plausible rival explanations (see Yin, 2003). The outcomes and analysis of the cases also includes policy implications, derived from impacts and impact narratives of the whole project. Note, that the framework and premises of conducting the case at hand and presented in this protocol excludes systematic causal analysis (1), universalizing the findings (2), and working without theoretical propositions or stance(s) (3).
Section 5: Outcomes and prioritization	
5.1 Plan validity	The validity, consistency and reliability of the research project will be assessed following Yin's (2003) plan validity, where applicable. Tactics for ensuring this include assessing the use of multiple sources of evidence, establishing chains of evidence, expert reviews of draft reports on cases, as well as member check. Hence, important aspects are (ibid.) a) construct validity; b) internal validity; c) external validity, and d) reliability. These aspects do not take place for instance only in the end of the research process, but dynamically during the different levels/phases of the process.
5.2 Primary and secondary outcomes	The primary outcomes of the research will explore and conceptualize the professionalism, professional work, and professional space of healthcare musicians in hospital wards. Outcomes will also identify the professional approaches of music-making in somatic healthcare and clarify the professional approaches of music and music education in healthcare settings. Secondary outcomes of the research will provide implications for future education, research, and practices in the field. Secondary outcomes may also review the “state of the art” in the research field related to the review, as well as enlighten the quality features of the research in the field. Publications will include published case studies, as well as a dissertation with synthesizing kappa, and a policy brief intended to the arts and healthcare organisations, as well as other stakeholders and policy makers in the field.
5.3 Risk of bias	To facilitate the assessment of possible risk of bias for each study, as well as the cross-case analysis, the critical appraisal guidelines or checklist will be visited, such as Atkins & Sampson (2002) or Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP, 2018), and used to summarize the quality appraisals across case studies.
Data synthesis and summary criteria	
5.4 Data synthesis and summary criteria	Quantitative meta-analysis will not be conducted. The pre-understanding of the main author is that the results of the data search are variable in diverse and fragmented ways, as well as the hypothesis that there will not be enough data to conduct meta-analyses. Heterogeneity will not be tested, nor any other quantitative methodology provided.
5.5 Assessing the body of evidence	As well as the assessment of (meta-)bias, the quality of evidence for all outcomes will be judged by the author(s), and by consulting other researchers, if necessary. Checklists and procedures for assessing qualitative meta-analyses and qualitative processes may be used, such as ENTREQ (Tong et al., 2012), general guidance and

	standards of JARS-Qual, inclusion in qualitative meta-analysis reporting (QMARS, Levitt et al., 2018).
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Appendix 1. Case report instructions for a single case (see Pucihar et al., 2015; Sieviläinen, 2013).

- A) Basic information on the case (responsible researcher, research context, participants, nature of data, case organisation).
- B) Data generation methodology
- C) Theories used
- D) Data-analyses
- E) Data set used, coding, other tools
- F) Validation of findings, confidentiality of data
- G) Other information